

Learning Outcomes of Students of Tourism Faculty, Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism - Influencing Factors

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to identify and evaluate the influences of factors on learning outcomes of students of Tourism Faculty at Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism. Based on the synthesis of theories and inheritance of previous researches, the authors proposed a model consisting of 6 main factors: student capacity, learning methods, learning attitudes, lecturer capacity, facilities, and social factors. After surveying 176 students using a structured questionnaire with 35 indicators and processing data using the PLS-SEM model, the results showed 5 positive - influencing factors on learning outcomes, in which learning methods had the strongest impact, followed by lecturer capacity, learning attitudes, facilities, and student capacity. The factor "family, friends and society" did not meet the reliability and was eliminated from the model. The study also proposed some practical solutions for students, lecturers and schools to improve training quality and learning outcomes. However, the study has some limitations in terms of survey scope, data collection time and has not mentioned psycho-social factors.

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KEYWORDS:

Students, Learning outcomes, Influencing Factors, PLS-SEM

1. INTRODUCTION

In the current trend of globalization and digital transformation, Vietnamese higher education is facing an urgent need for comprehensive innovation to improve training quality, meeting the increasing demands of the labor market. For the tourism industry - a key economic sector with rapid growth and high requirements for human resource quality, ensuring good learning outcomes for students is not only a measure of the school's training capacity, but also a decisive factor in students' ability to adapt and compete in their careers after graduation.

At Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism, improving students' learning outcomes, especially students of the Faculty of Tourism, is always identified as a key task. However, in reality, students' learning outcomes still have many shortcomings and are affected by many different factors. Therefore, it is necessary to systematically study the factors affecting learning outcomes. On that basis, this topic is carried out to determine the level of impact of each factor, thereby proposing practical solutions, contributing to improving the quality of students' learning and enhancing the effectiveness of training at the school.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS AND RESEARCH MODEL

2.1. Theoretical basis

Student learning outcome is a multidimensional concept, reflecting the level of achievement of educational goals during the learning and training process at the training institution. According to Le Thi Thu Lieu and Huynh Xuan Nhat (2009), learning outcomes are evidence of the success of learners in completing goals in knowledge, skills, abilities and attitudes. These are the basic pillars that form the comprehensive capacity of students in the higher education environment.

Young et al. (2003) argue that learning outcomes are overall assessment of the level of knowledge acquisition and skill development of students after studying specialized content. In addition to knowledge acquisition, the factor of applying knowledge into practice is considered an important measure, reflecting the depth and effectiveness of the training process. According to Nguyen Dinh Tho and Nguyen Thi Mai Trang (2010), the quality of lecturers - especially professional competence and pedagogical skills - has a direct impact on students' learning motivation and learning outcomes.

From the perspective of learners, Nguyen and Nguyen (2010) emphasize that learning outcomes are not only the product of assessment from the school, but also the students' self-awareness and assessment of what they have acquired, practiced and tried

to expand in the classroom. Sharing this view, Le Dinh Hai (2016) defines learning outcomes as students' overall assessments of the knowledge and skills acquired during the process of studying specialized subjects.

Furthermore, Dinh Thi Hoa et al. (2018) inherited the views of Tran Kieu (2005), emphasizing that learning outcomes should be assessed according to three core objectives: cognition, action and emotion. These elements not only help form academic thinking but also contribute to the development of comprehensive personal capacity.

From the above arguments, it can be affirmed that: students' learning outcomes are not simply academic achievements, but also the crystallization of professional knowledge, practical skills and positive learning attitudes. In this study, learning outcomes are understood as the level of students' self-assessment of professional capacity, soft skills and attitudes accumulated during their studies at university - factors that determine their ability to adapt and succeed in the future career environment.

2.2. Overview of factors affecting student learning outcomes

In the field of higher education, identifying and measuring factors affecting student learning outcomes has received widespread attention from researchers. In Vietnam, many scientific works have approached this issue from different perspectives, contributing to building a theoretical and practical basis for improving training programs, innovating teaching methods and improving output quality. Selective inheritance of previous research models is necessary to develop a model suitable for the training context at Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism. On that basis, the research team selected six typical works in Vietnam from 2018 to 2024 as a reference and comparison basis.

Specifically, the study by Dinh Thi Hoa et al. (2018) is one of the earliest works to mention the relationship between learning conditions and learning outcomes. The authors' model focuses on the following factors: facilities, teaching methods, learning methods and social factors. The study confirms that the overall learning environment plays a fundamental role in supporting students to achieve high results.

In 2020, the study by Phan Thi Hong Thao et al. (2020) continued to affirm the central role of learning motivation and methods. The proposed model includes five main factors: learning motivation, teaching methods, learning methods, facilities and family-social factors. This study has provided many practical suggestions for universities in adjusting teaching strategies.

A year later, Pham Thi Thuy Duong (2021) expanded the scope of the study by building a model consisting of six groups of factors: learning motivation, social networks, persistence in learning, quality of lecturers, facilities and family-social factors. Research data was collected at Tra Vinh University with quantitative testing techniques such as EFA and linear regression. The results showed that learning motivation and quality of lecturers were the two factors with the strongest influence.

Most recently, a number of in-depth works have continued to expand the scope of analysis and improve the reliability of model building. Do Thi Man (2024) conducted a survey of 500 students majoring in Economics and Engineering at Hong Duc University and used the Structural Equation Model (SEM) to examine the influence of seven factors: learning methods, learning motivation, teaching methods, training programs, facilities, support factors, and family and society. The results showed that learning methods and learning motivation were the two factors with the most positive influence.

Also in 2024, the research team of Nguyen Thu Huong and colleagues (2024) built a model including the following factors: friends, family - society, facilities, learning methods and teaching methods. This study especially emphasized the role of social factors and learning environment in forming students' motivation and positive learning attitudes.

Finally, the study of Le Thi Ngoc Diep (2024) was assessed as having the highest synthesis and system among the researched works. The author's model proposed 11 factors divided into two large groups: (1) the group related to learners including: learning attitudes, learning methods, student capacity, family - society and friends; (2) the group related to training institutions including: lecturer capacity, teaching methods, training programs, assessment methods, facilities and training management. The study was conducted using a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, allowing for a multidimensional and comprehensive assessment of impact relationships.

From the inheritance of the above research models, the group of authors has selected factors with high influence and suitable for the actual conditions of students of the Faculty of Tourism to build the proposed research model. This is to ensure scientific, practical and highly applicable in improving the quality of training at the school.

2.3. Research model on learning outcomes of tourism students at Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism, Vietnam.

Based on the selective inheritance of previous research works in Vietnam such as Le Thi Ngoc Diep (2024), Do Thi Man (2024), Nguyen Thu Huong et al. (2024), Phan Thi Hong Thao et al. (2020), Pham Thi Thuy Duong (2021), and Dinh Thi Hoa et al. (2018), the authors have built a proposed research model consisting of six main factors affecting the learning outcomes of students at the Faculty of Tourism, Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism. These factors were selected based on their popularity in previous models, while ensuring that they are suitable for the school's application-oriented training characteristics. Specifically, the research model includes: (1) Student capacity; (2) Learning methods; (3) Family, friends and society; (4) Lecturer capacity; (5) Facilities; (6) Learning attitude. The hypotheses proposed by the research team are as follows:

H1: Student capacity has a positive impact on students learning outcomes. Student capacity is an endogenous factor, reflecting the ability to absorb knowledge, independent thinking, self-study skills and the level of initiative in the learning process. In the current university education environment, students not only need to memorize knowledge but also flexibly apply skills such as communication, cooperation, problem solving and critical thinking. According to Le Thi Ngoc Diep (2024) and Pham Thi Thuy Duong (2021), students with high learning capacity often know how to set their own goals, choose appropriate learning methods, manage time effectively and actively participate in academic activities. They tend to study deeply, absorb well and easily adapt to changes in training methods. From that, it can be affirmed that learning capacity plays a decisive role in students' learning outcomes, and is the foundation for ensuring learning progress and quality throughout the training process.

H2: Learning methods have a positive impact on students learning outcomes. Learning methods are the way students organize, approach and process knowledge during the learning process. In the context of innovative education, learning methods are no longer limited to listening to lectures and taking notes but need to be personalized, creative and linked to practice. Studies by Phan Thi Hong Thao and colleagues (2020), Pham Thi Thuy Duong (2021), Do Thi Man and Nguyen Thu Huong and colleagues (2024) have shown that students who apply active learning methods such as group learning, project-based learning, using supporting technology, mind maps, learning through practical experiences... often achieve higher learning outcomes. These methods not only improve knowledge acquisition but also help students develop soft skills and maintain long-term learning motivation. Choosing the right learning method that suits your personal characteristics and the specific subject is a key factor in improving learning effectiveness in the university environment.

H3: Family, friends and society have a positive influence on students learning outcomes. The social environment is an ecosystem that has a profound influence on students' psychology, motivation and learning effectiveness. Family not only provides material conditions but also serves as a spiritual support, creates a stable foundation and orients learning values. Friends are a resource to support learning through knowledge sharing, group study and active competition. In addition, social factors such as scholarship policies, school culture, orientation communication and community environment also contribute to inspiring learning and forming a positive learning attitude. Studies by Do Thi Man (2024), Nguyen Thu Huong et al. (2024), Le Thi Ngoc Diep (2024), and Phan Thi Hong Thao (2020) all confirm that students with good support from family and society often have better learning outcomes. This shows the indispensable role of exogenous factors in promoting students' learning effectiveness.

H4: Lecturer capacity has a positive impact on students learning outcomes. Lecturers play a central role in organizing the teaching and learning process, guiding, inspiring and accompanying students. Lecturer capacity is demonstrated in professional qualifications, pedagogical capacity, ability to update new knowledge and apply information technology in teaching. According to Le Thi Ngoc Diep (2024), competent lecturers not only help students understand the lesson but also stimulate critical thinking, support professional skills and create a positive learning environment. The lecturer's use of appropriate methods, flexible learning activities and maintaining effective interaction with students will directly affect the motivation, attitude and learning outcomes of learners. Therefore, investing in developing lecturer capacity is a strategic solution to improve training quality and student learning effectiveness.

H5: Facilities have a positive impact on students learning outcomes. Facilities are essential conditions to ensure the quality of teaching and learning. Infrastructure such as classrooms, libraries, information technology systems, learning spaces, specialized practice rooms, etc. have a direct impact on students' ability to access knowledge and develop skills. Studies by Dinh Thi Hoa et al. (2018), Le Thi Ngoc Diep (2024), Pham Thi Thuy Duong (2021), and Nguyen Thu Huong's group (2024) all clearly show that adequate facilities not only facilitate academics but also enhance learning spirit, inspiration, and motivation for personal development. In the modern university environment, facilities act as a "catalyst" to support students in accessing knowledge proactively, effectively, and comprehensively.

H6: Learning attitude has a positive impact on students learning outcomes. Learning attitude reflects students' awareness, initiative, sense of responsibility and commitment to the learning process. This is a fundamental factor affecting the way they approach knowledge and the ability to maintain stable learning outcomes. According to studies by Le Thi Ngoc Diep (2024) and Pham Thi Thuy Duong (2021), students with a positive learning attitude often proactively develop learning plans, have clear goals, know how to self-evaluate and adjust their learning behavior. They do not learn to cope but aim for the sustainable value of knowledge and skills. Learning attitude also has the ability to spread and is influenced by the social environment, lecturers and friends. When learning attitudes are formed and maintained positively, students will develop comprehensively and achieve better learning outcomes.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. Data collection method

After developing the survey form, the research team conducted in-depth interviews with 5 people who are restaurant owners or restaurant managers with working experience for many years at the restaurant in Thanh Hoa city. The survey form was completed according to the comments of the interviewees, the research team conducted a random test survey on 10 people. The survey results

showed that the opinions agreed with the factors included in the survey, on that basis the research team conducted a large-scale survey via google form with the link:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfgxci9cqBA-6EEf1bl5ZPTFxRSXL0dbGhh-2x5s7jNuelNYQ/viewform?usp=sharing>

The data collection method was conducted by the research team based on the study of Höck & Ringle (2006) for reference on the expected sample size. Accordingly, the minimum sample size is 5 times the total number of observed variables. This is the appropriate sample size for research using Comrey factor analysis (1973): $N=5*m$, note that m is the number of questions in the survey. Therefore, the team of authors will survey the number of questionnaires as $N > 5*35 = 175$ (questions).

In order to collect data for the research model verification process, the authors conducted a survey of 200 students from the Faculty of Tourism, Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism using a random sampling method. The survey was conducted from February to April 2025. The survey consists of two main parts. The first part focuses on collecting personal information with 10 questions on demographic characteristics such as gender, year of study, major, place of residence, family economic conditions and frequency of use of technology devices to support learning. The second part includes 35 questions divided into 7 sections, corresponding to groups of factors in the research model such as: student capacity, learning methods, family - friends - society, lecturer capacity, facilities, learning attitude and learning outcomes. The questions were constructed on a 5-point Likert scale from “Totally disagree” to “Totally agree”, to measure the students’ perception and evaluation of each influencing factor.

The collected data were used to conduct quantitative analyses to test the reliability, validity and relationship between variables in the theoretical model.

3.2. Data processing method

In this study, the authors used quantitative research methods to analyze data collected from student survey tables, to test the theoretical model and proposed research hypotheses. Data were processed using SmartPLS 4.0 software, with the main analysis tool being the partial linear structural model (PLS-SEM), suitable for exploratory research and medium-sized samples. The assessment of the quality of the measurement model was carried out through criteria such as: outer loadings with a desired value ≥ 0.7 ; composite reliability and Cronbach's Alpha to measure the reliability of the scale; convergence was determined by the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value; and discrimination through the HTMT coefficient.

After ensuring the suitability of the measurement model, the authors tested the structural model by examining the path coefficient, the R^2 value to determine the level of explanation of the independent variables for the dependent variable, the f^2 coefficient to measure the individual influence of each independent variable, and the SRMR index to check the overall suitability of the model. The application of PLS-SEM in this study allows for the simultaneous assessment of the reliability, validity, and impact of each factor such as student capacity, learning methods, facilities, learning attitudes, etc. on learning outcomes, thereby pointing out the research implications as well as discussions.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive statistics of the research sample

The author sent a total of 176 survey forms to students of the Tourism Faculty of Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism. The questions in the survey forms were built on Google Drive due to accessibility conditions. The results obtained 176 responses (100% response rate). All of responses were valid, achieving a rate of 100%.

In 176 votes, male gender accounts for 35.8%. Female gender accounts for 64.2%.

Figure 1. Gender Distribution

The survey determined that out of 176 responses, 47.7% of students are studying Hotel Management. 35.2% of others are studying Tourism and Travel services Management. And the lowest percentage of 17% belonged to Tourism students.

Figure 2. Distribution by Academic Major

According to the survey results, fourth-year students account for the highest proportion at 30.7%, followed by third-year students at 25.6%. Second-year students make up 23.3% of the total, while first-year students represent the smallest group at 20.5%.

176 Responses

Figure 3. Academic Year Distribution

According to the survey of current accommodation of students of the Faculty of Tourism, Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism, it was determined that the majority of students (53.4%) are living in rented houses. Following that, there is also a large number of students (42%) who choose to stay at home to save costs. The number of students staying in dormitories and other accommodation accounts for a relatively small, almost insignificant proportion.

Student satisfaction with learning outcomes was also clearly reflected in the survey. 38.9% of students reported being satisfied with their academic results, while the proportion of dissatisfied students was relatively low at 14.2%. The largest group, 46%, considered their academic performance to be average. The number of students who reported being very satisfied was minimal and nearly negligible.

Figure 4. Satisfaction Level Distribution

4.2. Reliability Testing of Analytical Data

Table 1 presents the reliability statistics of the dataset, including Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). These are essential indicators used to assess the reliability of research data. The dataset is considered reliable when both Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values exceed 0.7, and the AVE is greater than 0.5. Accordingly, the analytical data meet the necessary reliability requirements for the following factors: Facilities, Lecturer Capacity, Student Capacity, Learning Methods, Learning Attitudes, and Learning outcomes of students from the Faculty of Tourism. However, the data for the factor "Family, Friends, and Society" does not meet the required reliability standard for model testing.

Table 1. Summary of Reliability Coefficients for Analytical Data

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)	Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)
Facilities	0.771	0.771	0.854	0.593	1.807
Family, Friends, and Society	0.679	0.688	0.822	0.607	1.041
Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	0.772	0.774	0.854	0.594	
Lecturer Capacity	0.906	0.909	0.941	0.842	1.603
Student Capacity	0.845	0.844	0.897	0.686	1.317
Learning Methods	0.865	0.870	0.909	0.714	1.229
Learning Attitudes	0.816	0.818	0.878	0.644	1.695

(Source: Author's data processing using Smart PLS)

4.3. Validation of Observed Variables

After removing the factor "Family, Friends, and Society" from the research model due to its failure to meet the required reliability for model testing, the model was re-run using Smart PLS 4 for the second time. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Summary of Construct Variables and Measurement Scales after Removing Irrelevant Items

	Facilities	Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	Lecturer Capacity	Student Capacity	Learning Methods	Learning Attitudes
CSVC2	0.726					
CSVC3	0.798					
CSVC4	0.799					
CSVC5	0.755					
NLGV1			0.939			
NLGV2			0.939			
NLGV3			0.873			
NLSV2				0.878		
NLSV3				0.861		
NLSV4				0.738		
PPHT1					0.764	
PPHT2					0.901	
PPHT3					0.856	
PPHT4					0.853	
PT1		0.783				
PT2		0.783				
PT3		0.766				
PT4		0.750				
TDHT1						0.790

TDHT2						0.809
TDHT3						0.819
TDHT4						0.791
NLSV1				0.828		

(Source: Author's data processing using Smart PLS)

The data in Table 2 shows that all indicator variables corresponding to the factors meet the required loading coefficients. These factors, along with their respective indicators, were included in the PLS-SEM analysis using Smart PLS version 4.1.0.9.

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) indicates the potential occurrence of multicollinearity in the model. A VIF value below 10 is generally acceptable; however, to ensure reliability, the VIF should not exceed 5 (Hair et al., 2011). According to Table 4, the VIF values for all variables in the model are below 5, indicating that multicollinearity is not present. This means that the relationships among the independent variables do not negatively affect the explanatory power of the model (as cited in Nguyen Dinh Tho, 2011).

Table 3: Summary of VIF Coefficients for Multicollinearity Diagnosis

	VIF
Facilities → Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	1.803
Lecturer Capacity → Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	1.585
Student Capacity → Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	1.315
Learning Methods → Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	1.229
Learning Attitudes → Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	1.680

(Source: Author's data processing using Smart PLS)

Discriminant validity of the model is ensured using the HTMT (Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio) index, which represents the average of all correlations between the observed indicators of one construct and those of another construct. An HTMT value greater than 0.90 indicates a lack of discriminant validity between two constructs, while the acceptable threshold should be below 0.85 (as cited in Nguyen Quang Anh).

Table 4: Discriminant Validity – Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	Facilities	Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	Lecturer Capacity	Student Capacity	Learning Methods	Learning Attitudes
Facilities						
Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	0.725					
Lecturer Capacity	0.615	0.700				
Student Capacity	0.560	0.534	0.346			
Learning Methods	0.424	0.645	0.437	0.248		
Learning Attitudes	0.702	0.704	0.588	0.493	0.369	

(Source: Author's data processing using Smart PLS)

The R² value (Coefficient of Determination) is a statistical measure used to assess the model's explanatory power or goodness-of-fit. According to Hair et al. (2011), R² values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 indicate strong, moderate, and weak explanatory power, respectively. In this study, as presented in

Table 5: Summary of R² Values

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	0.563	0.550

(Source: Author's data processing using Smart PLS)

Table 5, the adjusted R² value is 0.550, meaning that 55% of the variance in academic performance can be explained by the independent variables included in the model. The remaining 45% is attributed to factors outside the model and random errors. Therefore, it can be preliminarily concluded that the model fits the data reasonably well.

Table 6: Summary of f² Values

	Facilities	Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	Lecturer Capacity	Student Capacity	Learning Methods	Learning Attitudes
Facilities		0.031				
Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students						
Lecturer Capacity		0.089				
Student Capacity		0.039				
Learning Methods		0.150				
Learning Attitudes		0.056				

(Source: Author's data processing using Smart PLS)

The f² value indicates the effect size of a construct when it is removed from the model. According to Cohen (1988), f² values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 correspond to small, medium, and large effect sizes of exogenous variables. If the effect size is less than 0.02, it is considered to have no effect. In this model, none of the links show a low level of impact on students' academic performance.

4.4. Analysis of the Impact of Influencing Factors

The author conducted Bootstrapping in Smart PLS-SEM with a resample size of 5,000. Based on Table 7, we examine the p-values and T-values in the Inner Model and Outer Model. For statistical significance, the p-value should be less than 0.05, and the T-value should be greater than 1.96. The results show that all T-values and p-values are consistent with the research model.

Table 7: Results Identifying the Significance and Overall Impact of Factors (Using Bootstrapping in Smart PLS)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Facilities → Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	0.156	0.162	0.079	1.970	0.049
Lecturer Capacity → Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	0.248	0.243	0.080	3.113	0.002
Student Capacity → Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	0.149	0.148	0.068	2.181	0.029
Learning Methods → Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	0.283	0.288	0.063	4.525	0.000
Learning Attitudes → Learning Outcomes of Tourism Faculty Students	0.203	0.201	0.069	2.935	0.003

(Source: Author's data processing using Smart PLS)

Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR): This index indicates the goodness-of-fit of the research model. According to Hu & Bentler (1998), a model is considered to have a good fit when the SRMR value is less than 0.08. Based on the results shown in Table 8, the SRMR value of the research model is 0.051, which is lower than 0.08. Therefore, this condition is satisfied, indicating that the model is suitable for data analysis.

Table 8: Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) Reliability Index

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.069	0.069

(Source: Author's data processing using Smart PLS)

Based on the above test results, all proposed hypotheses can be accepted: H1, H2, H4, H5, and H6.

The standardized regression equation of the research model is as follows:

$$Y_{\text{LOoTFS}} = \text{Learning Methods} \times 0.283 + \text{Lecturer Capacity} \times 0.248 + \text{Learning Attitudes} \times 0.203 + \text{Facilities} \times 0.156 + \text{Student Capacity} \times 0.149$$

Figure 5: Final Model after Data Analysis using Smart PLS Software
(Source: Author's data processing using Smart PLS)

5. IMPLICATIONS OF THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

Firstly, the research confirms the positive influence of six key factors on the academic performance of students from the Faculty of Tourism at Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism. After developing the research methodology and conducting statistical testing using actual data, it was found that the following six factors impact academic performance: (1) Student Capacity; (2) Learning Methods; (3) Family, Friends, and Society; (4) Lecturer Capacity; (5) Facilities; and (6) Learning Attitudes.

Secondly, among these six factors, Learning Methods (2) were identified as having the strongest impact on student academic performance. This highlights the importance of choosing and applying effective learning strategies. Lecturer capacity (4) follows closely, emphasizing the essential role of educators in guiding and supporting students. Learning Attitudes (6) also play a critical role, demonstrated through students' active, positive, and committed engagement in the learning process. Facilities (5), while having a weaker influence, remain a necessary condition for effective learning environments. Student Capacity (1) - encompassing self-study ability, time management, and adaptability - also contributes to learning outcomes, albeit to a lesser extent.

Thirdly, the factor Family, Friends, and Society (3) was found to have no significant effect on the academic performance of Tourism students at Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism.

6. DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research results confirmed the theoretical model with five factors that have a positive impact on the learning outcomes of students of the Faculty of Tourism, Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism. In which, Learning method was identified as the factor with the strongest impact ($\beta = 0.283$), showing the importance of students choosing, applying and developing learning strategies suitable for themselves and the training content. Lecturer capacity ($\beta = 0.248$) and student learning attitude ($\beta = 0.203$) are also two key factors, affirming the indispensable role of a quality teaching staff and the spirit of self-awareness and initiative from the learners. Facilities ($\beta = 0.156$) and Student Capacity ($\beta = 0.149$) also have positive effects but at a lower level. Notably, family, friends and society factors were excluded from the model due to lack of statistical reliability, which partly reflects the increasing independence of students in the modern learning process.

These findings are consistent with previous studies such as those by Dinh Thi Hoa et al. (2018), Phan Thi Hong Thao et al. (2020), Pham Thi Thuy Duong (2021), and Le Thi Ngoc Diep (2024). All these studies emphasize the decisive roles of learning methods, lecturer capacity, and student attitudes in learning achievement. The convergence of results across studies suggests that the model proposed in this research has strong academic validity and closely reflects the current educational context at Vietnamese higher education institutions. Importantly, the exclusion of the "Family, Friends, and Society" factor aligns with recent research, indicating a shift in higher education where students are increasingly independent and less influenced by external social factors.

From the above results, the authors propose some recommendations as follows:

For students: It is essential to raise self-study awareness, proactively choose appropriate learning methods such as project-based learning, group learning, and exploit technology to support learning. At the same time, build a positive learning attitude, have clear goals, and regularly self-evaluate your learning process.

For lecturers: There is a need to continuously improve professional capacity and innovate teaching methods to motivate and inspire students. Increasing interaction and guiding students to learn proactively is necessary in the context of educational innovation.

For schools: It is necessary to continue to invest synchronously in facilities, especially digital libraries, smart classrooms, and open learning materials systems. In addition, the training programs should be implemented, focusing on soft skills and lifelong learning strategies to comprehensively enhance students' learning abilities.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND LIMITATIONS

The study has successfully built and tested a model of factors affecting the learning outcomes of students of the Faculty of Tourism, Thanh Hoa University of Culture, Sports and Tourism. Through the PLS-SEM analysis method, five factors were identified to have a positive impact on learning outcomes, including: learning methods, lecturer capacity, learning attitude, facilities and student capacity. In which, learning methods are the factor with the strongest impact, showing the leading role of students in choosing and applying appropriate learning strategies. The research results not only contribute to clarifying the theoretical basis of factors affecting learning outcomes but also provide useful practical data for schools, lecturers and students in improving training quality.

However, the study still has certain limitations. Firstly, the survey scope is limited to students of the Faculty of Tourism, so it does not fully reflect the learning situation of students in other majors in the school. Secondly, the data collection period took place in a short period (from February to April 2025), the use of self-completed questionnaires can lead to bias due to students answering less seriously or providing incomplete information. Thirdly, the research model mainly focuses on quantitative factors and has not considered other psychological and social factors such as learning emotions, financial pressure or academic support. Therefore, further studies should expand the survey scale, combine more qualitative methods such as in-depth interviews or field observations, and integrate more psychological and social factors to complete the model more comprehensively.

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